

Graphene Nanoribbons Derived From Zigzag Edge-Encased Poly(*para*-2,9-dibenzo[*bc,kl*]coronylene) Polymer Chains

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Supporting Information Placeholder

ABSTRACT: In this work, we demonstrate the bottom-up on-surface synthesis of poly(*para*-dibenzo[*bc,kl*]coronylene) (**PPDBC**), a zigzag edge-encased analog of poly(*para*-phenylene) (PPP), and its lateral fusion into zigzag edge-rich graphene nanoribbons (ZGNRs). Towards this end, we designed a dihalogenated di(*meta*-xylyl)anthracene monomer displaying strategic methyl groups at the substituted phenyl ring and investigated its applicability as precursor in the thermally induced surface-assisted polymerization and cyclodehydrogenation. The structure of the resulting zigzag edge-rich (70 %) polymer **PPDBC** was confirmed by scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) and non-contact atomic force microscopy (nc-AFM). Remarkably, by further thermal treatment at 450 °C two and three aligned **PPDBC** chains can be laterally fused into expanded, zigzag edged graphene nanoribbons (**ZGNRs**), with a ribbon width of nine ($N = 9$) up to seventeen ($N = 17$) carbon atoms wide. Moreover, the resultant **ZGNRs** exhibit a high ratio of zigzag (67 %) vs. armchair (25 %) edge topologies featuring electronic band gaps as low as 0.15 eV according to DFT calculations.

Nowadays, bottom-up synthesized atomically precise graphene nanoribbons (GNRs) represent an imperative class of one-dimensional graphene nanostructures because of their outstanding electronic and magnetic properties, which entirely depend on their molecular topology at a width scale below 5 nm.¹⁻⁴ Among all the bottom-up protocols for GNR synthesis in solution^{4,5} and by chemical vapor deposition (CVD)⁶ under ambient pressure, the on-surface approach under ultrahigh vacuum conditions (UHV) has the advantage of giving access to characterization by *in-situ* scanning tunneling microscopy (STM), scanning tunneling spectroscopy (STS) and non-contact atomic force microscopy (AFM) to reveal the geometric and electronic structure of the prepared GNRs with atomic resolution.^{2,7,8} Hitherto, a series of armchair,^{2,7,8} chevron,^{3,9,10} and few GNRs with other edge topographies - for example cove¹¹ and chiral¹² ones - have been reported for the on-surface synthesis. In 2016, a fully zigzag edged GNR (ZGNR) has been successfully synthesized on an Au(111) substrate using an “U-shaped” monomer.¹³ The key strategy employed is to take advantage of a methyl

group substituted umbrella-shaped precursor monomer forming a snake-like polymer chain in the first thermal annealing step. Subsequent methyl group activation provides access to absent carbon atoms in order to build up the zigzag periphery.¹³ In contrast to the rich portfolio of accessible monomer designs for the on-surface synthesis of armchair edged GNRs (AGNRs), so far this is the only exclusive design principle available for an entirely zigzag edged GNR. Therefore, precursor designs, which would allow to control the width of ZGNRs remain elusive. A simple explanation relies in the missing concept of the linear propagation of zigzag edge-rich monomer building blocks into laterally extended graphene nanostructures as it is commonly employed for achieving other edge topologies. In this respect, a zigzag edged equivalent of poly(*para*-phenylene) (PPP) would be highly desirable, but to the best of our knowledge, it has not been demonstrated yet.

Herein, we report the surface-assisted bottom-up synthesis of a fully zigzag edge terminated poly(*para*-dibenzo[*bc,kl*]coronylene) polymer (**PPDBC**, Fig. 1c) - a strictly linear zigzag edged derivative of PPP - by linear polymerisation and subsequent cyclodehydrogenation of 9,10-bis(4-bromo-2,6-dimethylphenyl)anthracene (monomer **1**, Fig. 1a). Remarkably, the resulting **PPDBC** chains undergo a “zipper process” leading to GNRs (Fig. 1d) with an extended alternating zigzag-armchair-periphery in a 6:1 ratio. Therefore, the strategy of **PPDBC** interchain merging can be utilized to synthesize laterally expanded GNRs (**ZGNR1**, **ZGNR2**) with different ribbon widths comprising zigzag-rich topologies, which lead to low electronic band gaps, e.g. 0.15 eV for **ZGNR2**.

Figure 1. Bottom-up on-surface synthesis of zigzag-enriched

graphene nanoribbons. Surface-assisted carbon-carbon coupling of (a) 9,10-bis(4-bromo-2,6-dimethylphenyl)anthracene (monomer **1**) on Au(111) under UHV conditions at 200 °C yields a (b) precursor polymer. (c) Subsequent cyclodehydrogenation ($\Delta T_3 = 350$ °C) provides sp^2 -hybridized, aligned **PPDBC** chains. (d) A further thermal annealing step ($\Delta T_4 = 450$ °C) enables an intermolecular zipping process forming **ZGNR1** and **ZGNR2** on surface.

As demonstrated in Figure 1a we designed and synthesized the dihalogenated di(*meta*-xylyl)anthracene molecular building block **1** comprising two methyl groups at each outer substituted benzene ring to reach a novel type of rhombic-shaped polymer chain (**PPDBC**) (Fig. 1c) by on-surface Ullmann-type polymerization and cyclodehydrogenation driven by strategic methyl group activation at elevated temperatures. Specifically, the synthesis of monomer **1** (Fig. 2a) commenced with the nucleophilic addition of 5-bromo-2-iodo-1,3-dimethylbenzene to 9,10-anthraquinone providing 9,10-bis(4-bromo-2,6-dimethylphenyl)-9,10-dihydroanthracene-9,10-diol **2** as intermediate compound, which has been used without further purification. Afterwards the crude mixture was treated with glacial acetic acid, sodium iodide and sodium hypophosphite monohydrate for 1.5 h under reflux to afford the desired monomer **1** (9,10-bis(4-bromo-2,6-dimethylphenyl)anthracene) in 38 % yield over both reaction steps. The chemical identity of monomer **1** was unambiguously confirmed by two-dimensional nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (NMR) (see Supporting Information) and high-resolution matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization (HR-MALDI-TOF) as shown in Figure 2b.

Figure 2. Synthesis and characterization of monomer 1. (a) Chemical reagents and conditions: (a) 5-bromo-2-iodo-1,3-dimethylbenzene, *n*-BuLi, THF, -78 °C, overnight, (b) sodium iodide, sodium hypophosphite monohydrate, glacial acetic acid, 135 °C, 1.5 h. (b) Liquid-state high-resolution MALDI-TOF spectra.

Thereafter, monomer **1** was deposited on a Au(111) single-crystal surface under UHV conditions and thermally annealed to induce and investigate the polymerization process. Self-assembled, closed-packed molecular islands of monomer **1** are detectable at room temperature (Fig. 3a). On-surface thermal annealing to $\Delta T_1 = 200$ °C induces debromination and aryl-aryl coupling reaction via activated surface-stabilized radicals. Initiated by a second thermal annealing step ($\Delta T_2 = 250$ °C) the covalently bonded precursor polymer wires (Fig. 1b) undergo already partial cyclodehydrogenation of the incorporated methyl groups. By treatment at $\Delta T_3 = 350$ °C the construction of fully planarized, highly uniform rhombic-shaped **PPDBC** chains, featuring an overall zigzag edge proportion of 70 % (detailed explanation for the assignment of edges, see Supporting Information), is completed (Fig. 3b). High resolution non-contact atomic force microscopy (nc-AFM) was employed to elucidate the molecular structure of **PPDBC** using a CO-functionalized tungsten tip attached to a quartz tuning fork.¹⁴ Figures 3c-d show tunneling current and nc-AFM images of a short **PPDBC** chain using the previously described technique in a con-

stant-height mode. The nc-AFM image clearly resolves the structure of a **PPDBC** segment with a length of ~ 10 nm and exhibit no defects at the chemical bond level, proving that the methyl group-based cyclodehydrogenation worked convincingly in a fully selective way. Due to the long-range alignment of the aromatic **PPDBC** wires and their characteristic reactive zigzag periphery a lateral edge fusion, the so called “zipper process” at $\Delta T_4 = 450$ °C, gives rise to atomically precise **ZGNRs** with zigzag edge-enriched geometry (Fig. 3e). The resulting zigzag edge proportion of **ZGNR1**, consisting of two laterally fused **PPDBC** chains, can be calculated to be 67 %. The percentage of zigzag periphery remains constant for further polymer chain fusions (see Supporting Information), e.g. **ZGNR2** involving three **PPDBC** segments.

Figure 3. AFM and STM images of highly aligned PPDBC chains and GNR bottom-up synthesis. (a) Molecular island of monomer **1** at room temperature, scale bar: 5 nm. (b) Thermal annealing at $\Delta T_2 = 350$ °C induces full zigzag polymer formation **PPDBC**, scale bar: 5 nm. (c-d) Constant-height current and nc-AFM image of a uniform **PPDBC** segment using a CO-functionalized tip, scale bar: 1 nm. (e) Second thermal annealing at $\Delta T_3 = 450$ °C produces graphene nanoribbons with diverse ribbon width and mixed zigzag-armchair periphery. The dashed white and blue rectangles highlight zipped GNRs (**ZGNR1**, **ZGNR2**) with double and triple width of **PPDBC**, respectively, scale bar: 5 nm.

Afterwards, the electronic band structures of **PPDBC**, **ZGNR1** and **ZGNR2** were theoretically calculated by density functional theory (DFT) (see Supporting Information). DFT has revealed a non-magnetic nature for the rhombic-shaped **PPDBC** system in gas phase and an electronic energy gap of $\Delta = 1.1$ eV (Fig. 4a). For higher-order polymers achieved through interchain fusion of **PPDBC** the band gap decreases with increasing ribbon width to about $\Delta = 0.85$ eV (**ZGNR1**) and $\Delta = 0.15$ eV (**ZGNR2**), respectively (Fig. 4b-c). Thereby, in comparison to previously reported 5- ($\Delta = 0.1$ eV),⁸ 7- ($\Delta = 1.6$ eV),² 9- ($\Delta = 1.4$ eV)¹⁵, 13- ($\Delta = 1.4$ eV)⁷ AGNRs and fully zigzag edged GNR¹³ the calculated electronic structures of **ZGNR1** and **ZGNR2** indicate an almost metallic behavior, suggesting the uniqueness of the zigzag edge-rich GNRs to be an important family of graphene nanostructures.

Figure 4. Width-dependent band structure calculations. (a) Single polymer strain PPDBC (1.10 eV). (b) ZGNR1 comprising two PPDBC chains (0.85 eV). (c) ZGNR2 comprising three PPDBC chains (0.15 eV).

In summary, we demonstrated the on-surface synthesis towards high quality, rhombic-shaped poly(*para*-dibenzo[*bc,kl*]coronylene) polymer chains, derived from a simple molecular polyphenylene precursor. The arising fully conjugated, aligned PPDBC nanowires with predominantly zigzag periphery and their exotic interchain-interaction paved the way for successful GNR fabrication with a zigzag edge content of 67 %, variable ribbon width and tunable electronic band structures. Prospectively, the combination of versatile substituted anthracene-like building blocks and the powerful on-surface chemistry approach enables to set up further multi-edged nanographenes in order to study their crucial physical properties such as band structure and magnetism.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website at DIO: [xxx](#).

Experimental section of monomer building block **1**, characterization by liquid-state NMR (^1H -, ^{13}C -, 2D-NMR) and high-resolution mass spectra (HR-MALDI-TOF, HR-ESI-MS) Furthermore details of on-surface sample preparation, STM and non-contact AFM measurements (PDF).

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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